

Getting started with proteomics

Welcome!

Wednesday 7 June 2023

The webinar will start at 1pm AEST /12:30pm ACST/ 11am AWST

Getting started with proteomics

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 [@AusBiocommons](https://twitter.com/AusBiocommons)

Acknowledgement of Country

We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and their custodianship of the lands on which we meet today.

We pay our respects to their Ancestors and their descendants, who continue cultural and spiritual connections to Country.

We recognise their valuable contributions to Australian and global society.

Housekeeping

Session is recorded

Autogenerated
captions available

Questions via Q&A
function

Proteomics & BioCommons

facilitate interactions with computational providers to build a more fit-for-purpose, flexible and cohesive data analysis ecosystem

Identifying challenges and proposing solutions

Identify

Research

Communicate

Document

Deploy

proteomics
researchers

proteomics core
facilities group

Proteomics Bioinformatics Infrastructure Roadmap for Australia

V4.0

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Current activities

Introductions

Australian Core Facilities and Proteomics Communities

Dr Luke Carroll

Technology Manager, Mass Spectrometry

Australian Proteome Analysis Facility

A/Prof Matt Padula

Director

Proteomics, Lipidomics and
Metabolomics Core

What is the proteome?

Open Reading Frame Product

Post-Translational Modifications

Aebersold *et al* Nature Chemical Biology volume 14, pages 206–214 (2018)

What we want to measure (but can't very well).

Amino Acid Sequence Variants

Why not directly analyse Proteoforms?

Why not directly analyse Proteoforms?

Intact proteoforms have multiple charge states.

Fragmentation spectrum is VERY complicated.

A Proteomics Experiment

Each of these steps can cause problems/bias if not properly controlled

- Smash everything open
- Divide the protein into groups
- Cut it up to peptides
- Divide the peptides into groups
- Measure peptide mass in the MS and smash the peptide to measure the fragments
- Search databases for matches
- Interpret what it all means biologically

Extracting Proteins

- What sub-proteome is being analysed?
 - Everything?
 - Cytosolic proteins?
 - Membrane proteins?
 - Protein complexes and interactions?
- Additives often not compatible with LC-MS/MS.
- If you can't extract it into a liquid, you can't analyse it.
 - Remove non-protein "contaminants".
- Solubilising proteins requires surfactants and chaotropes.
- No ability to amplify the number of molecules to increase sensitivity.
 - Can't simply load more.

Separating peptides

Injected Sample Band (Appears "Black") (Blue, Red, Yellow)

- A "peptide" is 1 – 100,000 plus molecules of EXACTLY the same thing.
- All molecules of a peptide migrate together in chromatography.
- The smaller the time window (peak), the higher the sensitivity.
- Chromatography has higher resolution with small molecules (tryptic peptides)

Molecules of Glu-Fib peptide

How do mass spectrometers work?

- Charged ions in gas phase (electrospray)
- Transmitted through quadrupoles.
- Select groups of ions for measurement or fragmentation and then measurement of fragments.
- Ion (peptide) mass and intensity is measured by:

Time of Flight

Data Dependent Acquisition (DDA)

MS1 scan – intact peptide ions

Data Independent Acquisition (DIA)

- DDA - select, smash, measure, repeat.
- Peptides can be missed.
- DIA - smash ALL peptides present, repeat.
- All peptides should be there.
- Why better?
- Less missing values.
- Better quantification.
- Re-interrogation of data with new questions.

Ludwig C. et al. DIA SWATH-MS tutorial *Molecular Systems Biology* (2018)

A Proteomics Experiment

Each of these steps can cause problems/bias if not properly controlled

Database searching - how it works?

- Single 1 hr DDA file has ~ 50,000 MS/MS scans
- Human proteome consists of ~20,000 reviewed proteins (UniProt) (80K unreviewed)
 - ~2.5 million unmodified peptides
- Proteins are digested to peptides, and spectra generated *in silico*, compared and matched to MS/MS data
- Highest scoring peptide returned as match
- Target-decoy strategy used to determine false discovery rate

10.1021/acs.jchemed.0c00853

Database selection

- Too small a database
 - Returns false positive matches from artificially high scores
- Too large a database
 - Returns false positive matches from closely related peptides that can not be in sample
- Are longer lists better?
 - Robustness, low missingness and high confidence identifications are critical for quantitative experiments

Protein group inference

Identification and quantification occur at peptide level BUT experiments reported at protein/gene group level

- Presence and abundance of protein inferred from peptide identifications
- Unambiguous assignment needs proteotypic peptides
- General guidelines require at minimum 2 peptides per protein to be identified
- Homologous peptides assigned to most likely protein / lead candidate

Packages and search software

- MaxQuant, FragPipe, DIA-NN
- Galaxy implements these tools
- Which you use doesn't matter, the result should be the similar
- Default settings are a good place to start

A screenshot of the Galaxy Australia web interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Galaxy Australia', 'Workflow', 'Visualize', 'Shared Data', 'Help', 'User', and icons for home, notifications, and a grid. The main content area is titled 'MaxQuant (test) (Galaxy Version 2.0.3.0+galaxy3)'. On the left, a 'Tools' sidebar lists various tools: Thermo RAW file converter, Prokka, MaxQuant (using mqp.par.xml), MaxQuant, MSstats, UniProt, Search engine output to Pin converter, Pout2mzid, Create nested list, Walnut, EncyclopeDIA, and Morpheus. The main panel shows the 'Input Options' for MaxQuant, including a dropdown for 'thermo.raw', a 'FASTA files' section with a file named '20: UniProt_Human_20230323.fasta', and fields for 'identifier parse rule' (containing '>([^\s]*)') and 'description parse rule' (containing '>(*)'). Below these are 'Search Options' with a dropdown for 'Nothing selected', a 'minimum peptide length' field set to 7, a 'maximum peptide mass [Da]' field set to 4600, and a 'minimum unique peptides' field.

A Proteomics Experiment

In vitro

In silico

Each of these steps can cause problems/bias if not properly controlled

Experimental design

Drug treatment - 72 h

- Distinct morphological changes
- Functional assay differences
- No significant differences in cell viability

Output and ideal results

Loading and intensity spread

Chromatogram

Log2 Intensity spread

Consistent ID and quantification

Heatmap for quantified proteins

Output and ideal results

Sample groups cluster and show distinct changes

PCA plot

Heat map of differences

Volcano plot

Variance

- Batch to batch variation biggest cause of instrument variability
 - Column changes
 - MS status
- Most technical variance comes from sample preparation

A Proteomics Experiment

In vitro

In silico

Each of these steps can cause problems/bias if not properly controlled

Experimental design

- Experiment needs to continue long enough have a change in protein turnover
- Will your experiment have an effect on protein expression?
 - Time point
 - Activity change
 - Morphological features
- Specific protocols to look at more dynamic changes
 - Phosphoproteomics

A Proteomics Experiment

In vitro

In silico

Each of these steps can cause problems/bias if not properly controlled

Protein extraction, digestion and clean up

- Extraction procedure can bias results
 - Membrane difficult
 - Some tissues require clean up due to high lipid content
- Use of protease inhibitors
- Trypsin and digestion efficiency
- Clean up required - can bias peptide recovery
- PTM enrichment

Peptide preparation

- Insufficient lysis / denaturation causing inefficient digestion
- Low material starting amount
- Presence of “contaminants”
- Sample loss during preparation
- Proteomic depth is dependent on sample type - poor sample preparation is also a cause

A Proteomics Experiment

Each of these steps can cause problems/bias if not properly controlled

Instrument variability, technical replicates and batching

- Instruments increase variability over time
 - Drift in chromatographic retention time.
 - Variation in ionisation.
 - Carry over in chromatography.
 - MS becomes dirty
- Technical replicates are a necessity to normalise data.

IEEE Access. 9.
24727-24737.
10.1109/ACCESS.2021.305
6955.

10.1038/s41596-021-00566-6

Consistent loading

- Quantification experiments rely on minimal technical variability
- Consistent sample loading key to obtaining good quality data
 - LC and MS technical issues
 - Accurate aliquots
 - Consistent clean up

A Proteomics Experiment

Each of these steps can cause problems/bias if not properly controlled

Number of IDs

- No amplification for proteomics
- Sample type has great effect on number of identified and quantified peptides/protein
 - 100s for simple matrix or those dominated high abundance proteins (plasma, serum, milk, isolated vesicles)
 - 3000 + for cell lines
 - Tissues can vary highly (2000 - 3000 for muscle; higher for brain)
 - May require specialised clean-up

[10.15252/msb.202210947](https://doi.org/10.15252/msb.202210947)

[10.1074/mcp.TIR119.001562](https://doi.org/10.1074/mcp.TIR119.001562)

Why can't I see the protein I'm looking for?

- 20,000 reviewed human protein in UniProt database and 80,000 total entries
- Typical experiments yield 10,000 - 20,000 peptides, 3000 - 4000 protein groups
 - Not in database?
 - Issues with lysis/extraction
 - Post translational modification
 - Digestibility
 - Low abundance
 - Poor quality spectra

Bottom-up proteomics are hypothesis generating experiments - we have other techniques that we can apply to assay for specific proteins!

A Proteomics Experiment

In vitro

In silico

Each of these steps can cause problems/bias if not properly controlled

Missingness

- Missing data a common problem in proteomics experiments
- Cause of missingness
 - Matrix effects
 - Limit of detection
 - Stochastic selection
 - Biological impact?
- DIA / labelling technical methods to overcome missingness problem
- Imputation to attempt to overcome in post-processing

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
A	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
B	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
C	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓
D	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓
E	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗

Statistics

- Relative quant experiment
 - Compare fold changes of peptides protein between samples
 - ANOVA or t-test
- Unadjusted p-values
 - Have to accept some false positives
- Cut-off values for p-value and fold-change
 - Typically $p < 0.05$ and FC of 1.5
 - 10s - 100s DE proteins

Heat map of differences

Volcano plot

A Proteomics Experiment

In vitro

In silico

Each of these steps can cause problems/bias if not properly controlled

What does it mean? Where to from here?

- Output of proteomics experiments is a list of identified, quantified and differentially expressed peptides and proteins
- Biological knowledge of the system is required to rationalise results
 - Pathway enrichment (Gene Ontology, STRING etc)
 - Integration with other 'omics data
 - Correlation with metabolism changes?
 - Orthogonal validation
 - Specific pathways / drug targets

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2021.12.013>

[10.1016/j.mcpro.2023.100508](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcpro.2023.100508)

Where to learn more

Training / courses / webinars

Search
TeSS

HuPO
Proteomics
timeline

EMBL-EBI
Training

MaxQuant
Summer
School

Galaxy Training
Network

Platforms / tools / workflows

Galaxy Australia

Australian
AlphaFold Service

Monash Proteomic
Analyst Suites

DIA-NN

FragPipe

Take aways

Know your biology and seek advice

- Experimental design needs to be carefully considered
- Sample preparation is major cause of non-biological variance
- Talk to the proteomics facility *BEFORE* starting your experiment

What's being measured

- Proteomics measures and quantifies peptides and infers protein abundance
- Proteomics compares fold changes of peptides/protein between samples

How to analyse your data

- There are lots of packages available to analyse your data and lots of places to learn more about them
- QC plots can give you clues to help you troubleshoot your experimental design

Questions?

Join the conversation

Australian BioCommons Proteomics Analysis Community

Quarterly meeting and presentations

Google Group Forum

☆ Proteomics Analysis 23 members

Welcome to the Australian BioCommons Proteomics Community Group

This group is for any Australian researcher (or their International collaborator)

- discuss proteomics analysis tools and pipelines with the group
- receive email updates or meeting invites on shared national infrastructure
- influence how that infrastructure is developed so it is support their research

NOTE: To post messages to the group, you will need a google account (or

NEXT ...

Genomic data - improving discovery and access management

14 June 2023

<https://www.biocommons.org.au/webinars-workshops>

Tell us what you thought ...

Feedback survey

Thanks for joining us!

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